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Inside-out growth in the early Universe: a core in a vigorously star-forming disc

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Local to redshift $z \sim 2$ universe

- We see many (quiescent) bulge and (star-forming) disc galaxies locally (Kormendy+2004, Simmard+2011 and many others)
- But of course: local spiral galaxies are not the progenitors of local ellipticals
- To find these progenitors we need to probe much more distant galaxies
- Multiple bulges at redshift 2, Lang+2014, Tacchella+2015, How do they assemble?

Tacchella+2015

Galaxy selection

- Chose possible targets from JADES NIRCам imaging of GOODS-S with F410M and F335M coverage
- Selected galaxies with a spectroscopic redshift in the range $z=7-7.8$ to probe some of earliest galaxies whilst still having the Balmer break
- Make no claims about population statistics but will explore in the future!

JADES Release v1
GOODS South

1 arcmin

F115W F277W F444W

Rieke+2023

We find this 3-
component galaxy at
 $z=7.4$!

- Spectroscopic NIRSPEC confirmed redshift of **7.4**
- Central **core** component
- Surrounding **disc** component
- **Clump** offset from the **disc** component

NIRSpec Spectrum

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Colour gradients

- Clearly visible colour-gradient

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ForcePho

- ForcePho (Johnson+ in prep) is a forced photometry tool that fits multiple PSF convolved Sersic profiles simultaneously to each filter <https://github.com/bd-j/forcepho>

- We use it to fit a three-component model

- Central **Core**

- + **Disc**

- + **Clump**

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ForcePho fits

- Can see how ForcePho models the components well in each band

ForcePho Fits

- Corner fit showing fluxes and sizes for the **Core** and **Disc** components

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Surface Brightness Profile

- PSF convolved model fits the data well (F356W)
- Can see how PSF smears out **Core** and **Disc** to larger radii

SEDs

Core Component

- SED fitting with Prospector (Johnson+ 2021)
- Non-parametric SFH (Continuity prior, Leja+ 2019)
- Two component dust model (Charlot & Fall 2000)
- $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 8.39$
- $t_{\text{half}} \approx 51\text{Myr}$
- $\text{SFR} \approx 3 M_\odot/\text{yr}$

Disc Component

- Fit independently, but with the same fitting routine
- $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 8.3$
- Relatively young ($t_{\text{half}} \approx 23\text{Myr}$)
- $\text{SFR} \approx 10 M_\odot/\text{yr}$

Clump Component

- Fit independently, but with the same fitting routine
- Can see that the clump has a distinct stellar population \rightarrow might be a small merging galaxy?
- $\log(M_*/M_\odot) = 7.2$

Star-formation histories

- **Disc** appears to be undergoing a recent burst
- **Core** appears to be decreasing in SFR
- **Core** and **Clump** appear to be older, **Disc** appears to be younger

Surface Density profiles

- **Disc** responsible for most star-formation seen, but **Core** responsible for most of the stellar mass in the central region → inside-out growth?

Mass-size

How does this compare to the local universe?

- The **core+disc** plotted against local analogues (Hopkins et al. 2010)
- **Core**: pretty massive and dense!
- Within x2 of local massive ellipticals despite 1000x less massive overall

Conclusions

- Find **Core**, **Disc** and **Clump** components in a spectroscopically confirmed redshift 7.4 galaxy
- **Disc** is relatively young ($t_{\text{half}} \approx 23\text{Myr}$) and strongly star forming ($\text{SFR} \approx 8 M_{\odot} / \text{yr}$)
- **Core** appears to be older ($t_{\text{half}} \approx 51\text{Myr}$) and more massive ($\log(M_{*}/M_{\odot}) = 8.39$) - possibly a proto-bulge?
- Detection of inside-out growth in the early universe
- Likely a progenitor of the kind of much more massive galaxy we see in the local universe!

One and two
component
fits

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AGN? – probably not

SFMS

Combined Photometry

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